

Report

The best available science describing type-approval testing methods and protocols for ballast water management systems that render nonviable organisms in ballast water

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Summary

The Vessel Incidental Discharge Act of 2018 (VIDA) became law on December 4, 2018, amending the definition of ‘live’ and ‘living’ for the purposes of the Ballast Water Regulations and instructing the United States Coast Guard (USCG) in coordination with the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), to publish a draft policy letter, “based on the best available science, describing type-approval testing methods and protocols for ballast water management systems, if any, that...render nonviable organisms in ballast water” and may be used “to measure the concentration of organisms in ballast water that are capable of reproduction.” VIDA indicates that the USCG “shall take into consideration a testing method that uses organism grow-out and most probable number statistical analysis” to measure the concentration of organisms greater than or equal to 10 micrometers and less than 50 micrometers ($\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ to $< 50 \mu\text{m}$) that are capable of reproduction.

The best available science relevant to VIDA’s instructions to the USCG and USEPA is reviewed here. The primary sources are the peer-reviewed literature and other documents that are available to the public. Key conclusions from this review include:

An appropriate testing methodology has been identified and accepted by the International Maritime Organization – The IMO has accepted the Most Probable Number Dilution Culture + Motility (MPN+M) methodology as one of two that may be used for enumerating viable organisms for type approval of ballast water management systems (BWMS). It was the only methodology found to be suitable for assessing treatment technologies designed to render living organisms non-reproductive. Disinfection with ultraviolet radiation is one such treatment technology.

The base method is well established and validated – The base method, serial dilution culture-MPN, was introduced in 1951 for use with multi-species communities of phytoplankton with unknown culturing requirements. The method has been described in UNESCO reference works and validated in peer-reviewed research, including studies of precision, range, detection limits, bias/trueness, and reproducibility.

Science supports the case for MPN – The USCG has questioned the reliability of MPN-based methods for ballast water testing, highlighting the need to culture all of the types of organisms found in ballast water, and uncertainty that organisms rendered nonviable will remain so over time. These and other concerns have been addressed directly — and effectively countered — in scientific publications, including expert opinion, peer-reviewed studies, policy analysis and evidence-based synthesis. The published assessments strongly support the case for MPN as a reliable efficacy test for BWMS type-approval testing. There is no available literature that challenges their findings.

Example applications of the methodology have been found to be suitable – Location-specific standard operating procedures (SOPs) have been used for BWMS type approval testing according to IMO guidelines. Methodological choices have been identified and their potential influences on testing efficacy have been estimated; acceptance of the MPN+M methodology by the IMO indicates that SOPs used in type-approval testing have been found to be suitable.

Validation for use in BWMS type-approval testing – A published framework for method validation includes quantitative criteria for evaluating the efficacy of testing methods for their intended use in a BWMS type-approval regime that requires five consecutive successful tests. A comparison of performance metrics, including limits of detection, precision and bias, indicates that MPN+M is equivalent or superior to the FDA/CMFDA + Motility method for effective enforcement of a BWMS performance standard for organisms $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ to $< 50 \mu\text{m}$ that are capable of reproduction.

In its guidance on methodologies that may be used for enumerating viable organisms $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ to $< 50 \mu\text{m}$ for type approval of BWMS (BWM.2/Circ.61), the IMO concluded that the MPN Dilution Culture + Motility methodology is suitable for assessing all BWMS treatment technologies, including those that render nonviable organisms in ballast water. This review of the best available science reaches the same conclusion.

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1. Introduction

The Vessel Incidental Discharge Act of 2018 (VIDA) was signed into law on December 4, 2018. VIDA amends the definition of ‘live’ and ‘living’ for the purposes of the Ballast Water Regulations (Section 151.1511 of Title 33) to exclude organisms that have been rendered non-viable. In accordance with the act, the United States Coast Guard (USCG) in coordination with the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), shall publish a draft policy letter, “based on the best available science, describing type-approval testing methods and protocols for ballast water management systems, if any, that... render nonviable organisms in ballast water” and may be used “to measure the concentration of organisms in ballast water that are capable of reproduction.” VIDA indicates that the USCG “shall take into consideration a testing method that uses organism grow-out and most probable number statistical analysis” to measure the concentration of organisms greater than or equal to 10 micrometers and less than 50 micrometers (10 to 50 μm size class), that are capable of reproduction.

By way of a circular, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) has accepted the Most Probable Number Dilution Culture + Motility methodology (MPN+M) as one of two that may be used for enumerating viable organisms for type approval of ballast water management systems, and the only methodology that is suitable for assessing treatment technologies designed to render living organisms non-reproductive (BWM.2-Circ.61, IMO, 2017). The methodology uses organism grow-out and most probable number statistical analysis to enumerate organisms that are capable of reproduction. Applications of the methodology have been used for more than a decade in evaluations of ballast water management systems (BWMS) for IMO type approval (Madsen and Petersen, 2015; Tobiesen, 2016). MPN+M thus represents the industry standard and best practice for measuring the concentration of organisms capable of reproduction in the 10 to 50 μm size class for type approval (TA) testing. There is a significant amount of industry experience, and a substantial body of scientific information available on the base method, MPN Dilution Culture, and on the use of MPN+M methodology in BWMS testing. The best available science is presented here for consideration in the development of the draft policy.

Consistent with VIDA, unless otherwise specified, ‘live’ and ‘living’ will not include organisms that have been rendered non-viable. In turn, the term ‘viable’ is synonymous with ‘living’ in this context.

2. Best Available Science

Despite its prominence as a requirement in the development of policy and regulations (Sullivan et al., 2006; Ryder et al., 2010; Esch et al., 2018), the term “best available science” has no relevant legal definition, thereby generating considerable debate (Bisbal, 2002). In practice, best available science can be defined in the context of management needs (Sullivan et al., 2006; Esch et al., 2018). Here, the context is evaluation of a BWMS testing method that uses organism grow-out and most probable number statistical analysis. Available science includes the conventionally accepted sources: peer-reviewed literature, the gray literature and expert opinion (Sullivan et al., 2006). Gray literature includes white papers, technical reports, government and intergovernmental documents, and conference proceedings. “Best” is a judgement call subject to many interpretations (Bisbal, 2002). Ryder et al. (2010, p. 823) identify common attributes of “best” scientific information: “it takes a form of peer-reviewed or published literature, expert

advice and, importantly, an acknowledgement that revision is necessary as uncertainties, limitations and inconsistencies are addressed over time.”

This summary of the best available science relevant to “type-approval methods and protocols for ballast water management systems that render nonviable organisms in ballast water” focuses explicitly on the MPN Dilution Culture + Motility methodology (IMO, 2017), specific examples of which were submitted to the Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC) of the IMO by Denmark and Norway (PPR 4/7, IMO, 2016c). The emphasis in this review is on the following sources of “best” scientific information:

- *Peer-reviewed literature* – Although it does not verify all reported results — this can be addressed in subsequent contributions by the authors or others — peer review is a formal process conducted by active, knowledgeable and independent experts to assess the validity of a scientific study by applying standards for methodology, reporting, interpretation and conclusions (Sullivan et al., 2006). The peer-reviewed literature relevant to MPN+M includes benchmark publications, scientific studies, and evidence-based synthesis. This scientific information can be considered to be best available science, subject to revision using the same peer-reviewed system.
- *Government and intergovernmental documents* – Official IMO documents (IMO, 2016a, 2017) and submissions to the IMO (e.g., IMO, 2016b, c), each have been developed through formal processes and are part of the permanent public record, thereby serving as best available science. As acknowledged in many of these documents, the science that they present is subject to revision as more information becomes available.
- *Published expert opinion* – Some documents are particularly valuable because they present expert opinions based on direct experience with methodologies. These include submissions by the United States (PPR 4/INF.10, IMO, 2016e), and, directly relevant to this summary, Denmark and Norway (PPR 4/7, IMO, 2016c). Both include detailed descriptions of methods (standard operating procedures, SOPs) and supplementary comments and evaluations.
- *Technical papers and conference proceedings* – If made readily accessible to the public in fixed form, for example on an institutional web site or archive, science is broadly available for consideration, comment and revision. The focus of this summary is on technical papers, scientific commentary and conference proceedings that are available to the public so the findings can be addressed and, as appropriate, revised over time.
- *Government statements and expert opinion on the permanent public record* – Fully accessible and directly relevant scientific information has been presented in the USCG Maritimes Common and in the congressional record. Expert opinion on the MPN method in the form of letters has been freely available since January 2016 at <http://mpnballastwaterfacts.com/expert/>.

Documents with restricted distribution – Scientific information on ballast water testing methods has been presented to the USCG, for example in requests to use an alternative method for TA testing and subsequent appeals (Coast Guard Maritime Commons, 2016). For the most part, these materials have not been published. ‘Available’ in ‘best available science’ does not specify available to whom. However, VIDA requires a period of public comment on the draft policy letter, and it is impossible to comment on a draft policy’s foundations if those foundations are unknown. This study will focus on science that is available to the public.

3. The MPN Dilution Culture + Motility Methodology

This review of best available science will focus on the MPN Dilution Culture + Motility methodology — i.e., its base methods — while identifying and evaluating elements of the methodology that can vary between applications, e.g., in location-specific SOPs.

The MPN+M methodology is used to enumerate viable organisms in the 10 µm to 50 µm size range (nominally protists, which includes both autotrophic and heterotrophic organisms) for TA (PPR 4/7, IMO, 2016c). Two base methods are combined: the serial dilution culture-most probable number method (SDC-MPN, also called MPN Dilution Culture) is used to estimate the number of viable photosynthetic organisms (autotrophs). Motile, nonphotosynthetic organisms are enumerated in parallel and counted as living heterotrophs (Heterotroph method). The two concentrations are summed to represent total living organisms.

3.1. Serial dilution culture-MPN: a well-established base method

The term SDC-MPN refers specifically to its use to enumerate photosynthetic microorganisms (Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a; MacIntyre et al., 2018b). The methodology is based on dilution culture, a technique used on phytoplankton for a century (Allen, 1919) and most probable number calculations, initially developed for interpreting results of sanitary analyses (McCrary, 1915). Introduced more than 60 years ago (Knight-Jones, 1951), SDC-MPN is an established approach for use with multi-species communities of phytoplankton. Significantly, the most abundant organism in Knight-Jones's dilution cultures was previously undescribed, demonstrating that prior knowledge of specific culturing requirements was not needed. The method is described in UNESCO reference works on phytoplankton methods (Thronsen, 1978; Andersen and Thronsen, 2003) and was recently reviewed in the context of BWMS testing (Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a). Generally, the method was used to isolate organisms for culturing and study, and also to enumerate species of phytoplankton that were difficult to preserve. More recently, it has been used in TA testing.

For over a decade, the SDC-MPN method has been used to enumerate viable phytoplankton in the 10 µm to 50 µm size range for BWMS TA testing according to the IMO G8 guidelines, which define the discharge standard in terms of viable organisms, characterized by the “ability to successfully generate new individuals” (MEPC.279(70), IMO, 2016a). The Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA), which was granted approval as a USCG test facility in 2015, has been testing BWMS according to the IMO guidelines using the SDC-MPN method since 2006 (Tobiesen, 2016). Similarly, DHI — approved as a USCG test facility in 2013 — has been conducting biological performance evaluations of BWMS using MPN-based methods since 2010 (Madsen and Petersen, 2015). The Golden Bear Test Facility – approved as a USCG land-based and shipboard test facility in 2018 (Safety4Sea, 2018) – has employed MPN-based methods going back to at least 2010 (Welschmeyer and Davidson, 2011).

3.2. Description of the SDC-MPN base method

The principles of the numerical MPN method (Cochran, 1950) are the same, whether for bacteria or phytoplankton.¹ A well-mixed sample is dispensed into a series of replicate culture tubes in tiers subject to serial dilution past the point at which some tubes contain no viable organisms and thus can show no growth. The most probable number of viable organisms in the undiluted sample is calculated from the results, making the key assumptions that organisms are randomly distributed in each tube and evenly distributed between subsamples, and that growth will be reliably detected in any tube containing one or more viable organisms.

The MPN method provides estimates of the concentration of viable phytoplankton in a parent sample based on:

- (i) its incremental dilution into a series of replicated liquid subcultures;
- (ii) incubation of the cultures under favorable conditions of light, temperature, and nutrients;
- (iii) scoring each tube for the presence of one or more viable organisms based on the detection of growth;
- (iv) probability-based estimation of the most likely number of viable organisms in the parent sample; and
- (v) calculation of concentration in the original sample from that number and the volume of inoculum in the tubes.

The SDC-MPN base method has been described in two UNESCO reference works (Thronsdén, 1978; Andersen and Thronsdén, 2003), reviewed in an evidence-based synthesis (Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a), and — as summarized by MacIntyre et al. (2018a) — validated in four laboratory studies (MacIntyre and Cullen, 2016a; Sun and Blatchley, 2017; MacIntyre et al., 2018a; MacIntyre et al., 2018b). Applications of the base method in TA testing, described in a submission to the IMO (PPR 4/7, IMO, 2016c) are discussed below.

3.3. The Heterotroph (motility) method

The MPN (autotroph) method is designed to enumerate only photosynthetic organisms. Non-photosynthetic organisms, called heterotrophs, comprise a relatively small proportion — 15% or less — of the microbes in the 10 µm to 50 µm size class (Wright and Welschmeyer, 2015; Blatchley III et al., 2018; Cullen, 2018). The Heterotroph method, based on observations of motility, is implemented in TA testing to enumerate this relatively small component of total organisms in the size range.

¹ For brevity in the following discussions “MPN” refers to SDC-MPN for the enumeration of viable autotrophs, unless otherwise specified. The method used for the enumeration of bacteria in sanitary analysis (McCrary, 1915) applies the same principles, but only the statistical assumptions and numerical analysis are relevant to BWMS testing.

The base method is described in PPR 4/7 (IMO, 2016c): a subsample of the original MPN sample is examined using epifluorescence microscopy to identify heterotrophs as those organisms that do not show the red fluorescence of chlorophyll. Those heterotrophs that are mobile are counted as “viable”. The Heterotroph method assesses a biological end-point of treatment — loss of motility — that differs from the intended end-point of disinfection with ultraviolet radiation (UV), loss of the ability to reproduce (Blatchley III et al., 2018). Overestimates of the number of reproductive organisms is thus expected. Expert opinion suggests that the overestimates may be large for treated discharge samples where the treatment includes UV-disinfection (PPR 4/7, IMO, 2016c).

Independent of uncertainties in the classification of organisms as living, the statistics of counting heterotrophs are the same as for the FDA/CMFDA + Motility method, also called the Stain-Motility method (Cullen, 2018), described in the Environmental Technology Verification (ETV) Protocol (NSF International, 2010).²

4. Implementation of the Methodology in Type Approval Testing

Applications of the base method for TA testing involve methodological choices that are reflected in specific SOPs, e.g., methods from three USCG-approved test facilities (DHI, NIVA, and the Cal Maritime Golden Bear Facility) that are available in the public record through the IMO submission by Denmark and Norway (PPR 4/7). The IMO submission also includes expert scientific evaluations of the methods based on years of experience. A great deal of additional science is available to guide and evaluate methodological choices for MPN+M: UNESCO reference materials (Thronsdén, 1978; Andersen and Thronsdén, 2003), evidence-based synthesis (Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a), laboratory studies evaluating best practices (MacIntyre and Cullen, 2016a; MacIntyre et al., 2018a), and a quantitative evaluation of uncertainties associated with elements of the methodology, including a review of the foundational literature on the more general MPN method (Cullen, 2018).

The sections below describe methodological considerations in the application of MPN methodology for TA testing.

4.1. MPN Matrix Design

Five methodological choices determine the MPN matrix design: the amount of inoculum per culture tube, the number of tubes per dilution tier, the number of dilution tiers, the dilution of the first tier of the series, and the dilution factor between tiers. As reviewed in recent studies (Cullen, 2018; MacIntyre et al., 2018b) and illustrated in Section 6, these choices determine the range of

² The FDA/CMFDA + Motility method is part of the USEPA Environmental Technology Verification (ETV) Program “Generic Protocol for the Verification of Ballast Water Treatment Technology” (NSF International, 2010), incorporated by reference into US type approval regulations. FDA and CMFDA are the fluorescent probes fluorescein diacetate and 5-chloromethylfluorescein diacetate, also called vital stains.

matrix resolution and precision of the estimates. The calculations are firmly established in the scientific literature (Cochran, 1950; Hurley and Roscoe, 1983; Jarvis et al., 2010).

Standard operating procedures from the three testing laboratories represented in PPR 4/7 (IMO, 2016c) each use a different matrix design that has proven to be effective in BWMS TA testing. For example, for each of three replicate matrices, DHI (see their Table 1) uses three tiers of 5 tubes each with an inoculum of 1 mL per tube and a dilution factor of 10x between tiers; dilution of the most concentrated first tier is adjusted so the range of matrix resolution fully encompasses the critical concentration to resolve in land-based and shipboard TA testing. Likewise, the NIVA SOP includes adjustments to matrix design to match matrix resolution with target values for inlet, control-discharge and treated discharge samples. The Cal Maritime Golden Bear Facility (Golden Bear) uses a single matrix design for all sample types — six tiers of 5, 3-mL tubes with a dilution factor of 6x between tiers, beginning with an undiluted first tier. Its range of matrix resolution is suitable for the full range of target values. Both the DHI-NIVA and Golden Bear approaches to matrix design have proven effective in analyzing samples for BWMS TA testing (PPR 4/7).

4.2. Incubation conditions

In their review of SDC-MPN for a UNESCO reference work, Andersen and Thronsen (2003, p. 128) concluded, “The success or failure of the method depends on (a) the cleanliness of the equipment; (b) the suitability of the growth medium; and (c) the external culture conditions (temperature and light).” Practitioners appreciate the need for cleanliness and employ procedures to ensure it (e.g., PPR 4/7); it is part of doing business when cultures are involved. In turn, each testing laboratory chooses incubation conditions to optimize the test method for local conditions, based on the best available science and direct experience. The procedures in PPR 4/7, in place for several years, are examples.

More recently, Cullen and MacIntyre (2016a) reviewed the relevant literature on incubation conditions for SDC-MPN, highlighting the benefits of maximizing the growth rates of organisms. They made provisional recommendations for growth medium preparation, temperature and light, emphasizing that the suitability of choices for TA testing of BWMS should ultimately be evaluated through empirical comparisons of results. Poor incubation conditions can lead to underestimates of the number of viable organisms, but, as confirmed by MacIntyre et al. (2018a; 2018b), no set of conditions can lead to systematic overestimates.

There is a direct way to determine if incubation conditions are suitable for TA testing: if a quantitative assessment of MPN testing efficacy relative to an accepted method are satisfactory (see Section 6.4), there is no compelling reason to question incubation conditions.

4.3. Detection of growth

Each MPN tube must be scored for the presence of one or more viable organisms based on the detection of growth. Detection of the initial presence of one or more viable organisms in a tube is determined by (i) the minimum number of organisms that can be detected reliably — a function of detector sensitivity and the signal per organism (generally, greater for larger organisms); (ii) the time it takes for a viable organism in the dilution culture to reach that threshold — a function of growth rate and a lag period, if any; and (iii) when the observations are made (Cullen and

MacIntyre, 2016a). Simply, a viable organism will not be detected if the final observations are made before the threshold concentration is reached.

The factors affecting the detection of growth in SDC-MPN have been examined in quantitative detail by Cullen and MacIntyre (2016a) and especially by MacIntyre et al. (2018b), who developed and described best practices for the application the base MPN method as a robust and repeatable assay of viable organisms in cultures of phytoplankton. Key elements relevant to TA testing include the development of criteria to score tubes as positive for growth and procedures to ensure that observations have been conducted long enough to ensure that most, if not all, viable organisms have had time to grow to the point of detection.

4.3.1. *Scoring tubes positive for growth*

As applied in TA testing for BWMS, it is the industry standard to use measurements of chlorophyll fluorescence — specifically, a change in the measured fluorescence over a 14-day incubation period — to determine growth. The three test facilities use different instruments to measure chlorophyll fluorescence and apply slightly different criteria for scoring tubes positive for growth, some including blank corrections and adjustments for instrument drift. For example, both DHI and NIVA score a tube as positive if measured fluorescence exceeds the average + four times the standard deviation of the blanks. The Golden Bear threshold is also based on the blank readings. The expert assessment in IMO PPR 4/7 concluded that state-of-the-art fluorometers were sensitive enough to prevent significant underestimation of the number of viable organisms in TA testing.

4.3.2. *Incubation time*

All three test facilities incubate the samples for a period of 14 days, a period that was judged to be adequate in the submission from Denmark and Norway (PPR 4/7, referring to unpublished results). An independent analysis provides support: the combined influences of this and other methodological choices were tested using empirical comparisons of MPN measurements with parallel enumerations of untreated organisms using the FDA/CMFDA + Motility method and there was no indication that the MPN methodology led to significant underestimation of the numbers of living organisms (Section 6.4.2).

4.4. MPN Calculations

Calculators or tables are used to determine the most probable number of viable organisms in the parent sample from the scores for the MPN matrix. Jarvis et al. (2010) derived calculations, adopted by ISO, that are applied in an Excel spreadsheet that is found in the ISO Standards Maintenance Portal (<https://standards.iso.org/iso/7218/>). The output values include MPN, its 95% confidence limits and test validity expressed as a rarity index. Unlike some other tables (e.g., Blodgett, 2010) the ISO calculations report an upper confidence limit on a result of zero tubes showing growth, and the lower confidence limit for results with all tubes showing growth; this allows explicit description of detection range (Section 6.1). Otherwise, results from commonly-used calculators are essentially equivalent to those from the ISO in the context of TA testing and method validation (MacIntyre et al., 2018a), so the choice of MPN calculator should have no influence on the efficacy of the MPN Dilution Culture method in TA testing.

4.5. Filtration of sample to isolate the > 10 µm size fraction

Samples may or may not be subjected to a filtration step designed to retain organisms ≥ 10 µm while allowing smaller organisms to pass through. The Golden Bear SOP includes a filtration step prior to analysis, while DHI's does not. The NIVA SOP indicates that it is optional and, where used, it should be validated that the practice does not reduce the viability of the species present in the sample. Potential biases associated with sample filtration are discussed in Appendix 2: filtration could lead to overestimation or underestimation of the concentration of living organisms 10 µm to 50 µm, whereas omission of the step will lead to positive bias (overestimation).

4.6. Heterotroph method

The DHI SOP describes the method for microscopic enumeration of living heterotrophs (Section 3.3). The criteria are observed motility and the absence of detectable chlorophyll fluorescence. The USCG-approved Golden Bear Facility enumerates living heterotrophs using flow cytometry and FDA-staining as part of their alternate implementation of the ETV Protocol for 10 µm to 50 µm organisms. The criteria are detectable fluorescence from the FDA vital stain, lack of chlorophyll fluorescence and suitable size. Notably, neither the DHI nor Golden Bear method is designed to exclude organisms that have been rendered incapable of reproduction but still show signs of life, and large overestimation bias is expected for discharge samples that have been treated with UV (Wright and Welschmeyer, 2015; IMO, 2016c; Blatchley III et al., 2018).

5. The Debate about MPN for Type-approval Testing

5.1. Major elements of the debate

In 2016, the USCG Maritime Commons blog stated that “MPN-based methods continue to be a highly-debated practice with regard to ballast water systems” (Coast Guard Maritime Commons, 2016). For examples, key concerns about the SDC-MPN method have been presented by the USCG in their 2012 final rule (US Coast Guard, 2012, 77 Fed Reg 57 p. 17274), in the Coast Guard Maritime Commons blog (2015, 2016) and in testimony by Rear Adm. Paul Thomas (U.S. Congress, 2016). The USCG position has been that the required ETV Protocol is a reliable and repeatable efficacy test and the MPN method is not (U.S. Congress, 2016, p. 13). This side of the debate has been responded to in various ways, including evidence-based syntheses (Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a; Cullen, 2018), conference presentations (Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016b; MacIntyre and Cullen, 2016b; Cullen and MacIntyre, 2017), industry experience and evidence-based expert opinion presented in Denmark and Norway's submission to the IMO (IMO, 2016c), policy analysis (Blatchley III et al., 2018) and experimental assessments of the SDC-MPN method (Hull et al., 2017; Lundgreen et al., 2018; MacIntyre et al., 2018a; MacIntyre et al., 2018b). Details will be discussed in the following sections.

Addressing central issues in the debate, the evidence suggests that SDC-MPN, as applied to ballast water TA testing, is much less vulnerable to methodological uncertainties than has been suggested in critical descriptions of MPN-based methods:

- Notably, all species of phytoplankton need not “culturable” in the conventional sense; for accurate enumeration, a viable organism in a culture tube needs to divide only enough

times to be detected. Species are known to have this capability even though they are difficult to maintain indefinitely in laboratory culture (Thronsdon, 1978).

- Specific culturing requirements need not be known in advance. The method has been used routinely to isolate previously undescribed organisms (reviewed by Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a).
- A comparison of methods in a quantitative framework showed that MPN Dilution Culture + Motility was equivalent or superior to FDA/CMFDA + Motility for effective enforcement of the BWMS Performance Standard (Cullen, 2018).

The USCG has also raised concern over the ability for an organism to repair itself after UV damage (Coast Guard Maritime Commons, 2015). This is important because VIDA defines the term “render nonviable” as being “permanently incapable of reproduction”.

The possibility of delayed recovery after UV treatment has been examined directly in the peer-reviewed literature (Hull et al., 2017; MacIntyre et al., 2018b). As reviewed by Blatchley et al. (2018, p. 8079), the evidence from these studies and the background literature is clear: damage from UV is repaired quickly or not at all, and the MPN Dilution Culture method promotes any repair that might occur. Thus, based on the best available science, the MPN methodology for TA testing assesses permanent loss of the ability to reproduce.

5.2. Timeline of the debate

Peer-reviewed scientific information responding directly to USCG concerns about MPN-based methods started to appear in May 2015 (online open-access publication of Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a). Since then, evidence for continued two-way debate is scant. The United States has suggested that it is unclear whether the underlying MPN-based method has been validated (IMO, 2016d) and the ETV Program has been studying the method since 2013 with no published information. No challenges or corrections to any published findings in support of MPN for TA testing (i.e., from Section 5.1) were found in a search of the available literature for this review.

6. Method Validation

The need for rigorous validation of methods for TA testing is recognized by the United States and IMO. Addressing the issue in PPR 4/7/1, the United States has suggested that it is unclear whether the base method underlying MPN Dilution Culture + Motility has been validated. However, explicit criteria for validating methods to enumerate viable organisms 10 µm to 50 µm for BWMS type approval have not been established. For example, a rich literature describes approaches to the validation of chemical and biological analyses (e.g., Green, 1996; Mishalanie et al., 2016; Parshionikar et al., 2016), but the study describing the validation of the FDA/CMFDA + Motility method (Steinberg et al., 2011) included no explicit calculations of the method’s precision or limits of detection. This precedent suggests that detailed and prescriptive standards for method validation (e.g., Parshionikar et al., 2016) are not at this time appropriate for evaluating the efficacy of TA testing methods for the 10 µm to 50 µm size class.

Responding to the need for more available science to support the evaluation of the MPN Dilution Culture + Motility method as an alternative to the Stain-Motility method, Cullen (2018) published an extensive review of performance metrics for both methods, along with a framework for comparative validation. The open-access, peer-reviewed publication has been available since

20 February 2018. The framework includes quantitative criteria for evaluating the equivalence of methods for their intended purpose — use in type approval testing of ballast water management systems. None of findings have been countered in available literature. Subject to revision, ideally in the peer-reviewed literature, this framework for method validation can be considered to be part of the best science available science. It is used to guide the following discussion of method validation.

Performance metrics – In general, methods for regulatory submission must include studies on specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, range, detection limit, quantitation limit, and robustness (Green, 1996). The definitions of these terms can vary depending on the method and application (Parshionikar et al., 2016). For example, specificity is equivalent to detection bias as defined by Cullen (2018) and considerations of linearity are inherent to evaluation of MPN. Metrics of performance for MPN Dilution Culture + Motility are reported for categories defined below.

6.1. Range of resolution

As described in section 4.1, the MPN matrix can be designed so that critical concentrations in TA testing can be resolved effectively. The “range of matrix resolution” is reported by DHI (PPR 4/7 Annex, Table 1): it represents the lowest and highest MPN values that are returned by an MPN calculator or table, excluding samples for which all culture tubes are sterile (reported as < the lowest non-zero value in the table) or all show growth (> the highest finite value). The range of resolution for any MPN matrix design can be described in this way; those used in TA testing have been shown to be suitable (section 4.1).

6.1.1. Lower limit of detection

MPN – Consistent with Frazier et al. (2013), the lower limit of detection (LOD) is defined here as the concentration of detectable organisms above which the probability of zero detects is < 5%. It is similar, but not identical to, the lower limit of the range of resolution. As illustrated by Cullen (Cullen, 2018, Eq. 13), the LOD for different matrix designs is readily calculated, based on well-established science (Jarvis et al., 2010). The limits for measurements on treated discharge should be low enough to provide statistical confidence that the method can discern concentrations of living organisms well below the discharge standard of 10 per milliliter (NSF International, 2010), and they do (Figure 1).

The LODs for inlet- and control-discharge samples should be low enough to ensure that concentrations of organisms below the minimum requirements (1000 and 100 organisms mL⁻¹, respectively) can be detected reliably. This requirement is satisfied for the three matrix designs reported in PPR 4/7.

Figure 1. Detection limits for the MPN and Stain-Motility methods. The analytical detection limit for an MPN matrix with undiluted sample in the first tier, $\min(LOD_{MPN})$, is shown as a function of tubes per tier for four culture inoculum volumes with a dilution ratio, $DR = 10$. The bottom line is for a 40 mL inoculum volume and $DR = 2$. The light grey arrows show the LOD_{S-M} for the Stain-Motility method corresponding to an examined volume of 3 mL for: 1x = no concentration (as described in IMO PPR 4/INF.10), and samples concentrated 10x and 30x before microscopy. The LODs for MPN matrix designs used in TA testing are well below the discharge limit of 10 living organisms mL^{-1} (From Cullen, 2018).

Heterotroph method – The Heterotroph motility method employs the same counting procedures as FDA/CMFDA + Motility and thus has the same LODs, as described by Cullen (2018).

Combined enumerations – The LOD for the Dilution Culture + Motility method would be the combined concentration of autotrophs plus heterotrophs for which the probability of *both* methods returning zero detects is $< 5\%$. The calculation has not been presented in the literature on TA testing and should be explored.³ Regardless, given the low LODs for MPN and the relatively small contributions of heterotrophs to total organisms, limits of detection for MPN+M can be considered to be suitable for TA testing.

6.1.2. Upper limit

In general practice, MPN dilutions can be chosen to avoid a saturated result of all tubes positive for growth (Cochran, 1950; MacIntyre et al., 2018b), but there is no point in doing this if the upper limit of the range of resolution greatly exceeds the regulatory standard, for example the minimum of 1000 living organisms mL^{-1} for inlet samples. The requirement is only to demonstrate that the standard is met, and when the minimum standard is greatly exceeded, the

³ Unpublished observations: The combined LOD should be less than the LODs combined. This is illustrated by the condition for which the probability of detecting zero autotrophs is $\sqrt{0.05}$ and the probability of detecting zero heterotrophs is $\sqrt{0.05}$. The probability of *both* methods detecting zero living organisms is the product, $p = 0.05$. The concentrations corresponding to $p = \sqrt{0.05}$ (i.e., $p = 0.22$) are one-half the LODs based on $p = 0.05$ (Cullen, 2018) so the LOD for both methods combined would be one-half their sum.

calculators used in TA testing will report greater than the upper limit of resolution, e.g., “>16,000” for saturated inlet samples in the DHI protocol. As explained by Jarvis et al. (2010), the MPN for a test in which all tubes are positive for growth is infinity — not helpful in the context of TA testing. But the lower bound of the estimate, e.g., the lower probable concentration at $p = 0.025$, (LPC_{MPN}), is readily calculated (Wilrich, 2017), and this statistically-defined estimate can serve to demonstrate that the concentrations of organisms exceeded the minimum standard — e.g., 1000 and 100 living organisms mL^{-1} for inlet- or control-discharge samples, respectively. An LPC_{MPN} well above 10 living organisms mL^{-1} demonstrates that the MPN method is suitable for detecting exceedance of the discharge standard.

There is no inherent upper limit to the concentrations of living heterotrophs that can be resolved using microscopy or flow cytometry. Dilution can be employed (PPR 4/7).

6.2. Precision

Precision refers to the closeness of agreement between independent test results, obtained under stipulated conditions. It represents the influence of random measurement error and is often expressed in terms of the standard deviation of test results, or the coefficient of variation (CV, the standard deviation divided by the mean, in percent). A review of the MPN method for TA testing (Drake et al., 2016) highlights that the method’s precision, represented as the CV of triplicate samples (e.g., as in IMO, 2016c) is worse than for the FDA/CMFDA + Motility method. Wide confidence intervals on MPN estimates are expected (Cochran, 1950). The conventional interpretation is that a method with worse precision (wider confidence intervals) is inferior for testing.

The influence of precision in the MPN + Motility and FDA/CMFDA + Motility methods on the efficacy of TA testing was thoroughly reviewed in the context of TA testing, which requires 5 consecutive successful test results for approval (Cullen, 2018). The quantitative analysis is fully described in the publication and its supplementary materials; it guides the following analysis of method precision in TA testing.

6.2.1. Metrics of precision

It is well established (Cochran, 1950; Hurley and Roscoe, 1983; Jarvis et al., 2010) that the precision of the MPN estimate is described not by the CV and additive confidence intervals, but by the standard error of the logarithm of the estimate. Confidence intervals are represented by a multiplicative factor (FCI_{MPN}). In turn, uncertainties in microscope counts (i.e., from the Stain-Motility and Heterotroph methods) are related directly to the number of organisms counted (NSF International, 2010; Miller et al., 2011; Frazier et al., 2013). The appropriate metrics of precision for MPN were compared with CVs and confidence intervals for the Stain-Motility and Heterotroph method (Figure 2). As expected, it was concluded that MPN estimates were less precise (had greater confidence intervals) than those from FDA/CMFDA + Motility. Additional random measurement error from the Heterotroph method reinforces the conclusion that confidence intervals are wider for the MPN+M methodology as compared to the FDA/CMFDA + Motility methodology.

Figure 2. Metrics of precision. A. Precision of SDC-MPN, from 70,400 solutions of a general equation relating the standard error of the natural logarithm of the estimate to matrix design (from Hurley and Roscoe, 1983; MacIntyre et al., 2018b). Symbols are median values and vertical bars show 5th and 95th percentiles. FCI_{MPN} is the multiplicative factor for the 95% confidence intervals; it is not strongly influenced by inoculum volume, a major determinant of the limit of detection. B. Confidence intervals in percent for counting methods such as FDA/CMFDA + Motility and the Heterotroph method, showing results for $V_{\text{S-M}} = 3.0 \text{ mL}$ sample volume examined (1x) and for samples concentrated by factors of 10x and 30x. The concentration of detectable organisms is μ_{meas} . From Cullen (2018).

6.2.2. Interpretation of differences in precision

Extending the scope of previous studies, Cullen (2018) incorporated estimates of the precision of both TA testing methods into a thorough, quantitative evaluation of the influence of random measurement error on the efficacy of TA testing. Conventionally, it would be concluded that the MPN-based methods were inferior to Stain-Motility methods because they are subject to random measurement error that could lead to a greater rate of false approvals of BWMS. If type approval depended on the results of single test cycles, the conclusion would hold (Figure 3, single test). However, it was demonstrated quantitatively that the requirement for 5 consecutive successful results in BWMS type approval testing fundamentally changes the relationship between a method's precision and its effectiveness in ensuring compliance with regulations. As shown in Figure 3 (5-test results), false approval due to random measurement error is effectively eliminated for both MPN and the Stain-Motility method because it requires 5 consecutive underestimates, and false rejection due to a single erroneously high measurement is more likely for the method with wider confidence limits, imposing an extra margin of safety for MPN.

Figure 3. The influence of method precision on the efficacy of TA testing. Stain-Motility (S-M) refers to the FDA/CMFDA + Motility methodology. This figure is from Cullen (2018), where the context is fully explained.

The results of this study reverse conventional interpretations of efficacy based on method precision alone:

With respect to precision, the MPN Dilution Culture + Motility methodology, with its wider confidence intervals, is superior to the FDA/CMFDA + Motility methodology for its intended use in TA testing of BWMS.

This conclusion is supported with quantitative rigor in the open-access, peer-reviewed scientific publication (Cullen, 2018). It has been available since 20 February 2018, and no challenges or revisions have been published to date.

6.2.3. Repeatability and reproducibility

As summarized by Parshionikar et al. (2016), precision may be considered at four levels: within-lab repeatability, within-lab reproducibility, between-lab repeatability, and between-lab reproducibility. Repeatability (intra-assay precision) refers to measurements of the same analyte made under the same conditions over a short period of time.⁴ Reproducibility can be defined as the closeness of the agreement between the results of measurements of the same analyte carried out under variable conditions of measurement, e.g., within the same laboratory at different time

⁴ For MPN, this would involve replicate enumerations of the same sample, a procedure that is deemed unnecessary — compared to pooling results for the same number of tubes — for describing the uncertainty of methods based on the Poisson distribution (NSF International, 2010 p. 41).

or between laboratories. It would be influenced by the same errors that determine repeatability, plus any additional sources of error that might arise between independent implementations of the method.

Reproducibility of the SDC-MPN base method was been characterized in a laboratory study designed to ensure that the analyte — phytoplankton in cultures growing exponentially in specified conditions — were uniformly viable so the concentration of viable organisms could be determined independently using flow cytometry. An inter-laboratory validation study (MacIntyre et al., 2018a) included the developers of the experimental protocol (MacIntyre et al., 2018b) and two laboratories that had no previous experience with the method (Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences in Maine, and the Department of Biological Sciences at the University of South Carolina). The study demonstrated intra-laboratory and inter-laboratory reproducibility: the precision of three independent replicates per species measured in three laboratories was indistinguishable from expectation based on perfect adherence to method assumptions with no degradation of precision. Because the concentration of viable organisms could be measured independently with confidence, it was also possible to validate that the method enumerated viable organisms and heat-killed organisms with no bias (Section 6.3).

6.3. Trueness / bias

Accuracy is the closeness of agreement between a test result and the accepted reference value — an agreed-upon reference for comparison (ISO, 1994). It is affected by precision and bias, and bias can be represented by trueness, the closeness of agreement between the average value obtained from a large series of test results and an accepted reference value (ISO 5725-1). For BWMS testing, the reference value would be the “true” concentration of viable organisms, a property that cannot be measured in natural samples of plankton (Drake et al., 2016) but which can be measured in controlled laboratory experiments (MacIntyre and Cullen, 2016a).

6.3.1. Laboratory validation

Accuracy of methods for enumerating viable organisms can be determined in the laboratory if stringent procedures are followed to ensure that the organisms in cultures are uniformly viable or all killed (MacIntyre and Cullen, 2016a). Consistent with recommendations for validating the base assumptions of the FDA+CMFDA method (Drake et al., 2016; IMO, 2016e), the basis of the SDC-MPN method was validated using actively growing and heat-killed cultures (methods described in MacIntyre and Cullen, 2016a). As illustrated in Figure 4, an inter-laboratory validation conducted on three species confirmed trueness, the reliable detection of all viable organisms and no false-positive results (MacIntyre et al., 2018a). The results were fully consistent with the hypothesis that the SDC-MPN method enumerated all viable organisms, as had been demonstrated for 13 species of phytoplankton from 7 divisions (MacIntyre and Cullen, 2016a; Sun and Blatchley, 2017; MacIntyre et al., 2018b). The zero-rate of false-positive error was previously demonstrated for six species in culture (MacIntyre and Cullen, 2016a; Sun and Blatchley, 2017).

Figure 4. Inter-laboratory validation of the SDC-MPN method using measurements on actively growing and heat-killed cultures of phytoplankton. Concentrations of viable organisms (C_{viable}) were measured by flow cytometry and estimated with SDC-MPN (C_{MPN}). The organisms in growing cultures were confirmed to be 100% capable of reproduction. Replicates (1–3, from independent cultures) were assayed for three species, and assessments were made at Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences (BLOS), Dalhousie University (DAL), and the University of South Carolina (U-SC). The dashed line is the limit of detection (LLD_{MPN}). Heat-killed cultures all registered the same result of no detected growth and thus $C_{viable} < LLD_{MPN}$. Error bars are 95% confidence intervals; results are indistinguishable from expectation based on perfect adherence to method assumptions with no degradation of precision. Results also confirmed reliable detection of all viable organisms and no false-positive results. From (MacIntyre et al., 2018a).

6.3.2. Sources of bias in type approval testing

Several potential sources of systematic overestimation- or underestimation error in MPN-based methods (bias) have been identified and judged to have a relatively small influence on the enumeration of living organisms in the 10 μm to 50 μm size range. These include: i) inclusion of autotrophs > 50 μm in MPN estimates; ii) chain- and colony-forming autotrophs; and iii) grazing by heterotrophs (Appendix 1, also Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a). Competition between phytoplankton species in dilution cultures is irrelevant as long as the winner is detectable (Cullen and MacIntyre, 2016a). As recognized in the ETV Protocol for Stain-Motility (NSF International, 2010), and for MPN, accurate enumeration of dormant yet viable organisms in the 10 μm to 50 μm size class is challenging and may require alternate methods (Blatchley III et al., 2018).

Other sources of bias in the MPN+M and Stain-Motility methodologies as applied in TA testing were defined in a quantitative framework so their potential influences on testing efficacy could be estimated based on structured analyses of results (Cullen, 2018). Broadly, they are defined as detection bias (error in the identification of organisms as living) and retention bias (errors associated with filtration). These sources of systematic measurement error are discussed in Appendix 2. Available science suggests strongly that applications of MPN+M would satisfy stringent stand-alone acceptance criteria for efficacy, but there is not enough available information to apply validation criteria rigorously to either MPN+M or Stain-Motility methods.

As described in the following section, a comparative validation of MPN relative to an FDA/CMFDA + Motility standard can be used to evaluate the efficacy of MPN+M.

6.4. Comparative validation

For BWMS testing, the “true” concentration of living organisms in a natural sample of plankton cannot be determined (Drake et al., 2016; Cullen, 2018). Instead, the use of an accepted reference can be considered (Mishalanie et al., 2016), for example results from an accepted reference method (Parshionikar et al., 2016, p. 2-7). Given its acceptance by the USCG and IMO, FDA/CMFDA + Motility fits the definition of accepted reference method for the purposes of this review. A comparative validation of MPN+M relative to a Stain-Motility standard (Cullen, 2018) can thus serve to evaluate the method’s efficacy in BWMS TA testing.

6.4.1. Acceptance criteria

Arguing that “equivalent or superior to the original method for the intended purpose” (p. 11 in U.S. Department of Health and Human Services Food and Drug Administration, 2015) is appropriate guidance, Cullen (2018) adopted “MPN is equivalent or superior to [Stain-Motility] for effective enforcement of the BWMS Performance Standard” as the testable hypothesis for comparative validation.

Acceptance criteria for comparative validation included a maximum limit of detection for MPN (easily satisfied: see Section 6.1) and the demonstration that MPN showed no negative bias relative to Stain-Motility. The latter criterion is conservative because as illustrated in Figure 3, an MPN-based method will be more effective than a Stain-Motility method in TA testing if neither is biased relative to the other. Further, the MPN-based method can have superior efficacy even if it underestimates living organisms (i.e., has a negative bias) relative to Stain-Motility (Cullen, 2018). It follows directly that a measure of the bias of MPN+M relative to an accepted reference method, FDA/CMFDA + Motility, will effectively test the suitability of the MPN-based method for type-approval testing of BWMS.

6.4.2. Factor of agreement

As discussed by Cullen (2018), an appropriate measure of the bias of one method relative to the other is the Factor of Agreement (FOA). For MPN and the Stain-Motility (S-M) method, the Factor of Agreement is $FOA(\text{MPN}, \text{S-M}) = X_{\text{meas}}(\text{MPN}) / X_{\text{meas}}(\text{S-M})$, where X_{meas} is the measured concentration. The logarithm of the ratio, $\ln[FOA(\text{MPN}, \text{S-M})]$, can be called the Relative Protection Index (RPI) because overestimates are considered to be conservative, and thus more protective of the environment in a TA testing regime (US Coast Guard, 2012; Frazier et al., 2013). The RPI represents the influences of both random and systematic measurement error in each method, including the possibility that positive bias (e.g., from $< 10 \mu\text{m}$ organisms included in MPN) compensates for negative bias from ungrowable organisms in MPN (IMO, 2016c; Cullen, 2018).

On first principles described in the study, the RPI is expected to be normally distributed, and if there is no net bias of one method relative to the other, the mean will be 0. A result of $RPI \geq 0$ indicates that the MPN method is more protective than the S-M method. The analysis should be applied only to samples that have not been subjected to UV-disinfection because vital stains

greatly overestimate the concentration of living organisms after treatment with UV (Wright and Welschmeyer, 2015; IMO, 2016c; Blatchley III et al., 2018).

A frequency distribution of the Relative Protection Index ($\ln[FOA(MPN, S-M)]$) is presented in Figure 5. The critical conclusion is that because $\ln[FOA(MPN, S-M)]$ is not significantly less than 0, there is no evidence to reject the hypothesis that the two methods provide equivalent protection (Cullen, 2018).

When the S-M method is considered to be an accepted reference for the concentration of living organisms, the FOA represents a direct measure of bias (see Appendix 2), and stringent single-method validation criteria can be applied. Considering S-M as an accepted reference method, the results in Figure 5 indicate that MPN+M has no significant negative bias. This result, along with the documented precision and LODs of the MPN method, shows that MPN+M satisfied the stringent acceptance criteria for single method validation (Cullen, 2018 Table 2).

Figure 5. Frequency distribution of the Relative Protection Index ($\ln[FOA(MPN, S-M)]$) for 64 land-based tests conducted by DHI between March 2011 and December 2015. The RPI analysis and its interpretation are documented in the original publication (Cullen, 2018), with details in its Appendix D. The index is a minimum estimate for MPN+M because heterotrophs are not included.

7. Status of Method Validation

In 2016, the United States opined that it was unclear whether the base method underlying the SOPs proposed in PPR 4/7 had been validated (PPR 4/7/1, IMO, 2016d). Much scientific information has been made available since then. Has MPN Dilution Culture + Motility been validated? Before considering an answer, it is helpful to review the distinction between methodology, a base method and SOPs.

The ETV Protocol describes the FDA/CMFDA + Motility method, an example of the methodology (e.g., as identified by the IMO in its circular BWM.2-Circ.61). One application of the methodology was validated by Steinberg et al. (2011). Later, a generic version of FDA/CMFDA + Motility was submitted to the IMO for consideration (PPR 4/INF.10, IMO, 2016e). These two applications of the methodology differ: for example, the Steinberg et al. (2011) method includes a filtration step to concentrate organisms whereas the IMO version does not. This difference was not considered to compromise the validation status of the base method: FDA/CMFDA + Motility without filtration can be accommodated if validated to the satisfaction of the Administration (PPR 4-INF.10). The United States identified other departures from the validated method that may be needed to optimize its use, such as staining with FDA singly for fresh water samples (Reavie et al., 2010) or enumeration of living organisms with a flow cytometer (a method used by the Golden Bear Facility). These are all variations on the base method, just as the three SOPs in PPR 4/7 are variations on the MPN Dilution Culture + Motility methodology. Consequently, an assessment of validation applies to the methodology, not a particular application of it.

This review has provided a substantial body of evidence, much of it peer-reviewed, to indicate that the MPN Dilution Culture + Motility methodology has indeed been validated for use in TA testing to measure the concentration of organisms in the 10 µm to 50 µm size class that are capable of reproduction.

8. Conclusions/Summary

The best available science — predominantly from the peer-reviewed literature — provides ample support for the development of policy describing type-approval testing methods and protocols for ballast water management systems that render nonviable organisms in ballast water. Key conclusions from this review of the best available science include:

- The IMO has accepted the Most Probable Number Dilution Culture + Motility (MPN+M) methodology as one of two that may be used for enumerating viable organisms for type approval of ballast water management systems. Of the two, it is the only methodology that is suitable for assessing treatment technologies designed to render living organisms non-reproductive.
- The base method, serial dilution culture-MPN, is well established, introduced in 1951 for use with multi-species communities of phytoplankton with unknown culturing requirements. The method has been described and validated in the peer-reviewed literature, including studies of precision, range, detection limits, bias/trueness, and reproducibility.
- Criticisms of MPN-based methods circa 2016, encapsulated as, “The testing method required by the USCG is a reliable and repeatable efficacy test and the MPN method is not” have been effectively countered in recent peer-reviewed publications. A search of the available literature found no subsequent challenges to these findings.
- MPN Dilution Culture + Motility is a methodology. Example applications include standard operating procedures (SOPs) that have been used for over a decade to enumerate viable phytoplankton for BWMS type approval testing according to the IMO G8 guidelines. Location-specific methodological choices have been identified and their

potential influences on testing efficacy have been estimated; acceptance of the MPN+M methodology by the IMO indicates that SOPs used in TA testing have been found to be suitable.

- A recently-published framework for method validation includes quantitative criteria for evaluating the efficacy of testing methods for their intended use in type approval of BWMS. A comparison of performance metrics, including limits of detection, precision and bias, indicates that MPN+M is equivalent or superior to FDA/CMFDA + Motility for effective enforcement of the BWMS Performance Standard.

In its guidance on methodologies that may be used for enumerating viable organisms $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ to $< 50 \mu\text{m}$ for type approval of BWMS (BWM.2/Circ.61), the IMO concludes that the MPN Dilution Culture + Motility methodology is suitable for assessing all treatment technologies, including those that render nonviable organisms in ballast water. This review of the best available science reaches the same conclusion.

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11. Biographical Sketch

Dr. John Cullen, FRSC, is Professor Emeritus of Oceanography at Dalhousie University. He has studied the physiology and ecology of phytoplankton, ocean observation systems, the effects of ultraviolet radiation on plankton, and technologies for assessing the efficacy of ballast water treatment. A pioneer in the development of ocean observation technologies, Cullen is a Fellow of Royal Society of Canada, The Oceanography Society, and the Association for the Sciences of Limnology and Oceanography (ASLO). Along with Dr. S.W. Chisholm of MIT, he received ASLO's Ruth Patrick Award for the application of basic aquatic science principles to important environmental problems.

Appendix 1: Potential sources of error from PPR 4/7

The IMO submission by Denmark and Norway provides a summary of the potential sources of error and bias in both the FDA/CMFDA + Motility and MPN Dilution Culture + Motility methodologies (PPR 4/7, Tables 2 and 3). Table 3 is reproduced here for convenience.

	Bias on number of living 10 to 50 μm organisms	Probable magnitude
Autotrophs		
<p>Inclusion of > 50 μm autotrophs Water samples are not screened through a 50 μm filter to remove > 50 μm autotrophs, which can result in an overestimation bias.</p>	Overestimate	<p>In many cases this bias is expected to be small, as > 50 μm autotrophs are typically rare (< 3% Chl in > 50 μm size fraction, Welschmeyer, personal communication). Additionally, the majority of BWMS include a filtration step designed to remove the organisms in the > 50 μm size class down to < 10 organisms/m³. Where filtration is part of the treatment, the Discharge Treated sample will have very few organisms that are > 50 μm, reducing the potential overestimation bias.</p>
<p>Inclusion of <10 μm autotrophs Samples may or may not be filtered on a 10 μm filter and resuspended, to remove < 10 μm autotrophs. Where 10 μm filtration is not employed, < 10 μm autotrophs will be present in the sample. This will result in an overestimation bias.</p>	Overestimate	<p>This bias can be large depending upon the mixtures of taxa in a given sample.</p>
<p>Non-growing autotrophs Some species of autotrophs may not be able to grow (reproduce) in the supplied culture conditions (media, temperature, light). This can result in an underestimation bias.</p>	Underestimate	<p>This bias can be minimized by providing optimal incubation conditions (general growth media; preparation of media using sterilized local water to which the community is already acclimated, incubation temperatures near ambient, low to intermediate light levels). Attempts to measure the bias have been made. The work showed that the bias approached 0% as higher level taxonomy was applied, and any bias was balanced by the ability of the MPN assay to detect and enumerate species that were below the detection limit of microscopic methods.</p>
<p>Slow-growing autotrophs Some species of autotrophs may not be able to grow (reproduce) fast enough to result in the detection of growth in the time frame of the assay. This can result in an underestimation bias.</p>	Underestimate	<p>This bias is expected to be small, given suitable growth conditions, time frames and suitable fluorometer sensitivity. Slow growing species are generally larger, but have proportionally more chlorophyll due to their larger volume. A model relating these factors shows that species of cells over the 10 to 50 μm size range will grow fast enough in a 14-day period to allow the detection of growth using fluorometers with state-of-the-art sensitivity (Petri, 2015).</p>

	Bias on number of living 10 to 50 µm organisms	Probable magnitude
<p>Chain- and colony-forming autotrophs Some species of autotrophs are able to form chains or colonies of individuals. This can result in an underestimation bias. The MPN dilution culture method requires cells to be dispersed, so that tubes at the point of maximum dilution will contain either one or zero living cells. With chain- or colony-forming species, the point of maximum dilution will contain either one or zero living chains or colonies (of multiple individuals). Thus the resulting MPN estimate will be an underestimate, of a factor equivalent to the number of cells per chain or colony (if such a value were constant). However, many of these species are < 10 µm in minimum dimension (e.g. chain-forming cyanobacteria, some of the chain forming diatoms). Since those organisms are not in the 10 to 50 µm size class, their presence will result in an overestimation bias.</p>	Under- and Overestimate	It has been observed in samples from test facilities that chain lengths and colony sizes may be shortened by disruptions like pumping and tank agitation. Gentle agitation of samples should significantly reduce chain lengths and colony sizes (Cullen and Macintyre 2015).
<p>Grazing by heterotrophs The presence of heterotrophs in any MPN tube can lead to grazing of autotrophs. This can result in an underestimation bias.</p>	Underestimate	This bias is expected to be small: grazer concentrations are expected to be lower than autotroph concentrations from ecological principles, so it is unlikely that grazing rates will exceed autotroph growth rates in a given MPN tube to result in a false no-growth signal. In addition, for the same reason grazers should disappear by dilution at lesser dilutions than autotrophs, so higher dilutions (where MPN resolution is determined) should be unaffected by grazers.
Heterotrophs		
<p>Assessment of live-dead status In this method, motility is used to judge the viability status of heterotrophs. Some treatment technologies like UV disinfection prevent organism reproduction, which does not result in the immediate loss of motility in heterotrophs. This results in an overestimation bias in Discharge Treated samples where the treatment includes UV disinfection.</p>	Overestimate	This bias may be large for Discharge Treated samples where the treatment includes UV disinfection.
<p>Assessment of live-dead status Viable but not moving heterotrophs are assessed as dead</p>	Underestimate	

Appendix 2: Additional information on sources of bias

Sources of bias in the MPN+M and Stain-Motility methodologies as applied in TA testing were defined in a quantitative framework so their potential influences on testing efficacy could be estimated based on structured analyses of results (Cullen, 2018). The analysis complements the expert assessments from Norway and Denmark (Appendix 1). Bias was defined in two categories: detection bias and retention bias.

Detection bias

MPN Dilution Culture method

Some viable phytoplankton in an MPN incubation may not reproduce to the point of detection under the conditions provided, but the weight of evidence shows that the problem of these “ungrowable” phytoplankton is not as severe as previously thought (Section 5.1).

“Ungrowable” but viable organisms influence the MPN estimate in direct proportion to their relative abundance in the sample (Section 5.3.2 in Cullen, 2018). Enumerations of species that appear in MPN grow-outs can be used to calculate a lower-bound estimate of the individuals that do grow in an MPN test. It is a low estimate because some species that grow in the cultures can be missed because they are outnumbered by more abundant or faster-growing species. The corresponding estimate of the proportion of ungrowable organisms is therefore an upper bound. It is an overestimate of the potential for false-negative bias.

The taxonomic approach has been included as a complement the MPN methodology (PPR 4/7, Wright and Welschmeyer, 2015; IMO, 2016c), but a comprehensive and quantitative analysis of false-negative detection bias is not available. Both experts (Appendix 1) and a review of available science (Cullen, 2018) found no evidence that the MPN+M method was significantly compromised by false-negative detection bias.

Heterotroph method

As explained in Section 3.3, the Heterotroph method assesses a biological end-point of treatment — loss of motility — that differs from the intended end-point of UV-disinfection, loss of the ability to reproduce. The expectation of overestimating the number of reproductive heterotrophs after treatment with UV is thus well established (Blatchley III et al., 2018); experts in TA testing suggest that the overestimation bias can be large (Appendix 1).

The magnitude of bias from including non-reproductive organisms in enumerations of living heterotrophs after treatment with UV can be estimated roughly by comparing FDA/CMFDA enumerations with those from MPN (Blatchley III et al., 2018). Results for 307 separate samples (their Fig. 3) indicate that after treatment with polychromatic UVC radiation, reproductive organisms as enumerated with MPN were overestimated by a factor of roughly 1000 when assessed with FDA/CMFDA. That is, about 99.9% of the UV-treated organisms showed signs of life but could not reproduce. Considering that concentrations of heterotrophs are generally < 15% of autotrophs in the size range (Wright and Welschmeyer, 2015), it can be predicted that if the overestimation were 100-fold rather than 1000-fold when using motility in heterotrophs rather than vital stains as a criterion — or even 10-fold — the concentrations of apparently living heterotrophs in UV-treated treated discharge would still be high enough to match or exceed those of living autotrophs. This pattern of anomalously abundant “living” heterotrophs in treated ballast water was observed in TA testing of a UV-based BWMS (IMO, 2014). The implication is that motility-based Heterotroph results from MPN+M on UV-treated samples are inappropriately high. In principle, the reproductive ability of heterotrophs could be determined using an alternate approach. An estimate could be obtained by applying the observed treatment-related reductions

in the numbers of autotrophs (i.e., UV-treated-discharge autotrophs / control-discharge autotrophs) to the numbers of heterotrophs in the control-discharge sample.

The Heterotroph method is subject to several other potential sources of error including living heterotrophic microbes that do not move after being treated with stains and illuminated in the counting chamber (underestimation, Appendix 1), incorrect classification of autotrophs as heterotrophs because chlorophyll fluorescence was not detected (overestimation, Drake et al., 2016) and inaccurate application of size classification during microscopic examination (underestimation or overestimation). But the evidence reviewed above suggests strongly that the biggest source of error is extreme overestimation of reproductive heterotrophs after UV treatment.

Retention bias

As defined and reviewed by Cullen (2018, Section 5.2), retention bias refers to several potential biases associated with filtration of ballast water samples to retain or exclude organisms for analysis of the 10 μm to 50 μm size range. Errors can be introduced by: i) unintended retention of organisms $< 10 \mu\text{m}$ (IMO, 2016c; Molina et al., 2016; Trindade de Castro and Veldhuis, 2018), leading to overestimation, ii) losses of organisms within the size range due to passage through or retention on the filter, or iii) loss of viable organisms due to mechanical damage. The net bias could be positive or negative.

If a filtration step to retain organisms $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ is not used, the MPN Dilution Culture method will lead to overestimates due to inclusion of viable organisms $< 10 \mu\text{m}$ (PPR 4/7, IMO, 2016c). This could be a strong source of positive retention bias because smaller autotrophs greatly outnumber those in the 10 μm to 50 μm size class (Cullen, 2018); the overestimation would be tempered because smaller cells, although present in the culture tubes, may not be detected due to their small signal per cell (MacIntyre et al., 2018b).

Evaluating measurement bias in a validation framework

A quantitative framework was developed to evaluate the combined influences of detection and retention biases on the efficacy of TA testing for both the MPN+M or FDA/CMFDA + Motility methods, taking each method's precision into consideration (Cullen, 2018). Examples of quantitative acceptance criteria for single-method validation were presented in the study's Table 2: they are directly comparable to requiring that a generic single-test analysis is free from negative bias, with a CV of 8% or less — a stringent expectation for a biological method.

The statistical consequences of the 5-test requirement in TA testing (Section 6.2.2) provide a margin of safety that allows MPN testing methods to perform effectively even under the influence of moderate negative bias. That is, true concentrations of viable organisms in treated discharge must be below 5 per mL rather than the nominal standard of 10 per mL for a BWMS to have a 50% probability of passing (Figure 3). Available science suggests strongly that applications of MPN+M would satisfy stringent acceptance criteria (Cullen, 2018, Table 2), but there is not yet enough available information to apply the framework's single-method validation criteria rigorously to either MPN+M or FDA/CMFDA + Motility methods. Instead, a comparative validation of MPN relative to a Stain-Motility standard was described. The analysis indicated that neither method was significantly biased relative to the other. If the FDA/CMFDA + Motility method is used as an accepted reference, it results would be estimates of "true" values. Then, the comparative validation (Section 6.4) shows that MPN+M has no significant negative bias and thus meets stringent single-method validation criteria.